

Eurodoc signs on to the Civil Society for EU's manifesto 2024 EU ELECTIONS MANIFESTO

The European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc) signs on to the Civil Society for EU's manifesto "[2024 EU Elections Manifesto](#)".

National and International NGOs like Eurodoc are part of civil society and as such an essential part of any healthy democracy. Civil society often plays a key role in promoting and protecting the rule of law and fundamental rights. By signing the manifesto, Eurodoc joins the growing number of representatives of civil society that calls on the EU institutions to strengthen the role of civil dialogue and protect it as an essential element of European participatory democracy.

The statement was authored by the administrative board of Eurodoc 2023/2024

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The statement was approved by the member organisations of Eurodoc

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Eurodoc, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, is a grassroots federation of 25 national associations of early career researchers (ECRs) from 23 countries across Europe. Eurodoc was established in 2002 and is based in Brussels. As a representative of doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level, Eurodoc engages with all major stakeholders in research, higher education, and innovation in Europe.

